

A Synergistic Fault Tolerant Computer Design
for an N-Version Programming Environment*

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Abstract

This paper describes the design of an ultra-reliable, fault tolerant computer system that integrates a number of state-of-the-art fault tolerant techniques into a single, unified concept for achieving fault tolerance. The design stresses a synergistic combination of hardware and software fault tolerant techniques to achieve substantial performance improvements at the system level. The specific techniques combined include hybrid redundancy, N-version programming, interprocessor inter-stages, and a reconfigurable, redundant I/O network. The paper examines the implementation of the techniques in an advanced fault tolerant computer architecture.

Introduction

Much of the previous work on fault tolerant systems concentrates on some specific aspect of a fault tolerant system. Efforts to increase the level and duration of system reliability by minimizing voter complexity [1,2], utilizing redundant computer channels, ensuring source congruency [3], and reducing software failures with N-version programming [4] have sought to optimize individual subsystems. However, in practice, a system's reliability and fault tolerance is an aggregate of the total system's ability to simultaneously satisfy its diverse reliability requirements. Optimizing a specific subsystem with disregard or even at the cost of other subsystems may lead to optimal subsystem performance but sub-optimal system performance. To achieve optimum system performance we must design the total system first and then design the subsystems in a way that best achieves the total systems goals, not vice versa. The subject of this paper

is a design that achieves reliability and fault tolerance synergism through a unified systems approach.

From a total system point of view, the goal of a fault tolerant system is to survive a predetermined number of hardware and software failures, yet retain sufficient performance to perform the application software. The basic elements of a fault tolerant system, the power distribution system, the verified and validated software, the effector system, the computer, and the data communications system [5,6], must all be ultra-reliable and fault tolerant. Fig. 1 depicts the key system elements of a candidate architecture for achieving the broad architectural goals of a fault tolerant system. The sensors, effectors and the computation elements are integrated into an ultra-reliable, integrated digital system by an ultra-reliable data communication system, such as the dispersed sensor processing mesh (DSPM) [5,6,7].

FIG. 1 Key hardware element of the candidate fault tolerant computer

Although the fault tolerant communication network is an important part of the total system, this paper will concentrate on the fault tolerant computer. There are two reasons for this. First, an abundance of theoretical and experimental work [5,6,7] has already been done, by the

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author and colleagues, on the DSPM fault tolerant network. Secondly, the availability of the central computer is essential for executing both the application software, and the fault tolerant I/O's network creation and maintenance software.

Concept

The implementation of the ultra-reliable computer or communication network shown in fig. 1 is not a simple matter of using more reliable components. Ultra-reliable systems require more reliability than can be reasonably expected from components available for the foreseeable future. Achieving higher reliability than that achievable by a system's constituent parts is normally accomplished by designing systems with replicated components. Generally some variation on N-modular redundancy (NMR) [1,2,8] is used in which whole hardware systems are replicated. One of the most promising variations of NMR, hybrid redundancy, combines NMR and standby sparing to increase the system's reliability. Therefore, hybrid redundancy [1,2,8] was chosen as the most likely candidate for implementing an ultra reliable computer. The paper examines the issues concerned with integrating N-version programming into a hybrid redundancy architecture, and the architectural changes that result.

Hybrid Redundancy

Early studies [1,8,9] of reliable systems sought to maximize hardware reliability. A triplex hybrid redundancy system (see fig. 2) resulted from these studies. In this architecture three of the computers are active and share the voter and a rotary multiplexer. The remaining computers are retained as spares. In the event that a computer has failed the rotary multiplexer deactivates the failed computer and activates one of the spares. In addition the rotary multiplexer retains the ability to retry the failed processor at a later time.

FIG. 2 Basic hybrid redundancy

In the hybrid redundancy architecture the voter and multiplexer form the hardcore or that portion of the channel that must function for the channel to function. Accordingly, the hardcore must be made as simple as possible to enhance its reliability.

On the other hand, regardless of reliability, a microcomputer must have the power and sophistication required to execute the applications software. As the complexity of the applications software increases, the complexity and sophistication of the microcomputer also increases. Attempts to increase programmer productivity through the use of floating point arithmetic and high level languages (HLL) leads to further growth of the microcomputer's complexity.

In order to increase the reliability of the system in spite of the computer's complexity, the hybrid redundancy strategy uses multiple simplex computers. While the reliability of the computer portion of the hybrid redundancy architecture can be increased by adding more computers, each additional computer that must be managed by the hardcore increases the complexity and thereby decreases the reliability of the hardcore. Since the reliability of the hybrid redundancy system is the product of the reliability of the redundant computers and the reliability of the hardcore, the optimum hybrid redundancy architecture consists of the optimum number of computer channels (active and unpowered spares) and the simplest hardcore possible for the number of computers.

In the references cited [1,8,9], Siewiorek proposed a hybrid redundancy approach (see fig. 2) that minimized the complexity of the voter through lock-step synchronization and bit by bit identity comparison. The rotary multiplexer connects only three computers to the voter, so regardless of the number of computers (in excess of 3) that enter the multiplexer, the voter complexity does not vary as a function of the number of computers. On the other hand, the complexity of the rotary multiplexer varies with the number of computers. Therefore the reliability of the hardcore is directly related to the number of computers entering the multiplexer. In the hybrid redundancy architecture proposed by Siewiorek, the reliability of the hybrid redundancy architecture was calculated assuming powered spares and a complexity ratio (α) between the simplex computer and the hardcore of 1000:1. Siewiorek showed that the optimum hybrid redundancy system consisted of five computers (3 active and 2 spares) and that increasing the number of computers further only increased the complexity of the hardcore and lowered the total reliability.

As experimental fault tolerant systems [10,11] came into existence the data gathered showed that catastrophic random hardware failures were not the only significant source of system failure. Three other significant sources of system failure exist, software reliability, slow hardware degradation, and data congruency.

As application software increases in complexity, software reliability and methodologies [12] of improving software reliability become significant. Several potential solutions [4,13] have been proposed. Currently N-version programming is receiving the most attention. N-version programming attempts to circumvent generic software faults by running several versions of software derived from the the same software specification . The diversity between software versions is intended to prevent similar faults from simultaneously occurring in each version. However, the very diversity that inhibits simultaneous faults prevents lock step operation of the system since the channels no longer execute identical code using identical data. In addition, advanced redundancy management systems utilize considerably more complex voting strategies, such as rate windows, adaptive voting windows, and reasonability checks, to cope with the subtlety of drifting or slowly deteriorating sensors. Analytical redundancy management (ARM) [14], used to detect deteriorating sensors and estimate the correct values from a meld of other sensor data, adds even more complexity .

The complexity of the voter must be increased if the voter does not operate in lock step with identical data. However, if the complexity of the voter is increased to handle floating point voting and advance redundancy management techniques the hybrid redundancy scheme collapses under the weight of the voter complexity. To minimize the impact on system reliability the complex floating point and redundancy management must be done in software where existing system resources (CPU, Floating point coprocessor, memory, clocks etc.) can be used with little degradation of system reliability.

Other system complications result from the requirement for reliable data transfer within a fault tolerant computer system. Of particular interest is data originating on the DSPM network. Because each piece of DSPM data enters the fault tolerant computer through a single port, initially a specific piece of DSPM data is only available to the channel with the receiving port. However, proper operation requires the data to be reliably transferred to the other channels in such a way that the transferred data agrees with the source

data (source congruency). The interstages are used to assure source congruency for the data transferred between channels. The interstages are also used to provide reliable transfers between channels during the sophisticated redundancy management operations used in an N-version programming environment. Therefore, the interstages are not only a necessary consequence of simplex DSPM data, but the interstages are also a consequence of a N-version programming environment.

Advanced Hybrid Redundancy

To overcome the deficiencies of systems that emphasize a single dimension of system reliability, an advanced approach to system reliability must provide a simultaneous solution to multi-dimensional aspects of system reliability. Synergistically integrated reliability (SIR) combines a number of reliability methods, hybrid redundancy, N-version programming, congruent data interchanges, and hybrid redundancy management (redundancy management achieved by the collaboration of hardware and software) to simultaneously achieve software and hardware reliability.

The configuration of the SIR architecture is a response to the environment in which the architecture must operate, thus to understand the design we must look at the environmental factors and the design decisions that they produce. The overall architecture, shown in figure 1, resulted from earlier work [15] on reliable data communication networks. The DSPM [16] studies determined four to be the minimum number of ports acceptable for ultra-reliable operation, while the basic hybrid redundancy (BHR) architecture (see fig. 2) supports only one port. Further the BHR architecture is designed to implement the redundancy management as a simple hardware vote in the hardware. The architecture is not designed to integrate hardware voting with sophisticated redundancy management software that is resident on the computer. Of course the architecture can be forced to support these strategies, but the result would be awkward and unnecessarily complex. The necessary interaction between the redundancy management software resident on the computer and the hardware suggests a distributive architecture that dedicates a hardware to each computer (see fig. 3). Since the hardware is designed to be as simple as possible, this approach is not costly.

Each node (see fig. 4) in the SIR architecture is composed of the elements, computer, interstage, voter, and rotary multiplexer, necessary to implement hybrid redundancy, N-version programming, congruent data interchanges, and hybrid redundancy management.

FIG. 3 Overview of SIR architecture

FIG. 4 Simplified node of SIR architecture

The Voter

In an N-version programming environment, the diversity between versions may cause even correct results to vary slightly from version to version. As a result, the identity comparison used in the BHR architecture is unsuitable for an N-version programming environment. However, as will be seen later, the data congruency and redundancy management still require an identity comparison. Therefore the voter must be capable of voting non-identical values, and performing identity comparisons. The mid-value voting strategy satisfies both criteria.

Mid-value voter

In order to minimize the complexity of the voter, rotary multiplexer, and inter-stage, the transfer, routing, and voting of data is done serially. In a serial implementation of the voter, a history of the previous decisions must be retained in order to make the current decision. Therefore, the voter is implemented as a finite state machine (fig. 5). In fig. 5, T0 is the initial state of the voting process. Transitions from T0 occur if the vote on the current bit indicates that one of the bits from A,B, and C is larger or smaller

than the bits from the other channels. Similar transitions are made from the next level, however, at the terminal level no further maximums or minimums cause state transitions.

To simplify the voter complexity and in deference to the voter's responsibility to communication with I/O devices over the DSPM network, the voter is designed to provide a midvalue vote on non-identical offset binary data (many of the DAC's and ADC's used in the I/O structure use offset binary) and identity votes on any binary representation.

FIG. 5 Mid-value voter state transition diagram

The preliminary design of the mid-value voter requires 41 gates and 4 flip-flops (not including circuitry for MAX and MIN outputs) compared to a 3 input majority gate (4 gates) for the BHR identity voter. Solely on the basis of complexity, the mid-value voter is a less reliable voter than the BHR identity voter. While the mid-value voting process could be made more reliable by implementing the voter in software, a software voter is much slower. In the DSPM system, the performance of the computer system was severely restricted by the poor performance of the interprocessor communication [5,16] and voting. Because voting and interprocessor communication are crucial parts of redundancy management, particularly in a N-version programming environment, the loss in voter reliability is a necessary tradeoff for high performance interprocessor communication and voting.

FIG. 6 SIR rotary multiplexer.

The Rotary Multiplexer

The rotary multiplexer routes data from the active computers to the interstage and routes data from the interstage to the other active computer nodes. In the BHR implementation, all of the redundancy management, voting, retries, and computer routing is done in the rotary multiplexer and the majority gate voter. In the SIR implementation, the redundancy management is much more sophisticated, hence most of the redundancy management is implemented as computer software rather than as hardware. As a result the complexity of the rotary multiplexer (see fig. 6) is actually reduced. On the other hand the SIR redundancy management requires the rotary multiplexer to support bidirectional communication which tends to increase the multiplexer's complexity. The resulting gate complexity is summarized in table 1. As can be seen, the overall complexity of the SIR rotary multiplexer is significantly less than the BHR rotary multiplexer.

TABLE 1 Gate complexity of BHR and SIR rotary multiplexer implementations

	BHR	SIR
5 channel	132	62
6 channel	162	79

The Interstage

The final element of the hardware, the interstage, provides a method to reliably exchange simplex and redundant data between computer channels. In order to reliably exchange data, each channel must have copies of the data received by the other channels and the data must be voted to assure that the data from the other channels was transmitted correctly. A reliable data exchange is particularly important when a single copy of a piece of data (simplex data) enters the system through a single channel and the simplex data must be shared with the other channels. In the case of simplex data, the non-receiving channels do not have their own data to compare against the data transferred from the receiving channel. Therefore in the case of simplex data, particular care must be taken to assure source congruency of the transferred data with the original copy.

Maintaining source congruency is particularly important to the SIR architecture because the DSPM network can provide essentially simplex data by routing all the channels of a redundant set of sensors through a single DSPM port. The interstage assures the source congruency by transferring the data to each channel by three separate paths and voting the result. In addition, the originating channel receives copies of the data received by the other two channels.

To maintain source congruency, the originating channel, for example channel A (see fig. 7), loads its simplex data into all three interstage registers. In the second phase the three interstage registers transfer their contents to the associated interstages. The home register is simply recirculated, but the other two registers are transferred to the other two active computer channels.

In the third phase, each interstage performs an internal exchange to load the transferred data into all three interstage registers. At this point all the interstage registers contain the original data. In the fourth phase, the contents of the interstage registers are again cross linked. As a result, each interstage contains a copy of the data received by the other interstages. In the fifth phase, the contents are voted. If the result of the mid-value vote indicates no decision (no min, no max) then the data transfer is correct. If the vote indicates that a channel is either a maximum or a minimum value, then the data associated with the channel was corrupted in the transfer and the transfer path is suspect.

FIG. 7 Interprocessor communication and voting through an interstage.

Concluding Remarks

The research into the synergistic fault tolerant architecture is in the preliminary design phase. The initial implementation will facilitate N-version programming, reliable communications, and sparing (for extended duration reliability). The initial implementation will form the core of a testbed to conduct experiments on. Once completed, the testbed will be used to examine a multitude of important fault tolerant computing issues such as the validity of N-version programming and the trade-offs between software and hardware reliability.

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